

Shared RDM Services & Infrastructure

Framework conditions for Shared RDM Services in Austria

Alexander Bardel¹

¹ Graz University of Technology, Austria

*Correspondence: Alexander Bardel, alexander.bardel@tugraz.at

Abstract

Efficient and sustainable research data management (RDM) requires not only institutional commitment but also well-coordinated, scalable infrastructures and services that transcend organizational boundaries. In Austria, a dedicated Open Science Policy [1] addresses these challenges and opportunities, providing a foundation for concrete implementations that benefit the national research landscape. The Austrian project Shared RDM Services and Infrastructure [2] responds to this need by developing and implementing a national portfolio of shared RDM services to support research institutions across the country.

Launched in July 2023, this three-year initiative brings together twelve Austrian universities with the shared goal of establishing a sustainable, interoperable, and user-oriented RDM infrastructure. The project is part of the Cluster Research Data initiative (Forschungsdaten.at) [3] and is funded by the Austrian Federal Ministry for Women, Science and Research (BMBWF). Its vision is to provide a framework in which institutions can offer high-quality RDM services to their researchers—without having to develop and maintain every component independently.

The project is structured into several interrelated work packages, each focusing on a specific aspect of shared RDM. This contribution will highlight the following key areas:

- Cooperative operating models for RDM software solutions
- Machine-actionable Data Management Plans (maDMPs): DAMAP
- Electronic Laboratory Notebooks: eLabFTW
- Repository systems: InvenioRDM

The project builds on the results and experiences of the completed FAIR Data Austria initiative [4]. Universities involved in that previous project are also partners in Shared RDM Services & Infrastructure, contributing valuable expertise across diverse disciplines that reflect the heterogeneity of Austria's research community.

A core outcome of the project is the design, implementation, and evaluation of modular operating models for shared RDM services. These models define roles, responsibilities, and support structures to ensure long-term sustainability and scalability beyond the project's duration. The insights gained are highly relevant for other national or regional initiatives aiming to establish cross-institutional RDM services. The project follows a collaborative approach in which universities with established RDM services act as supporting institutions, working closely with

pilot universities to co-develop and, where possible, implement operating models in real-world settings. Trust built during previous collaborations plays a crucial role in enabling equal partnerships and effective implementation. The adaptation of high-level operating models to institutional contexts is a key factor in ensuring successful integration into each pilot university's existing service ecosystem [5].

This contribution to CoRDI 2025 will present the project's objectives, current status, and key outcomes, with a focus on operating models and RDM software solutions. It will also reflect on the challenges of coordinating service development across institutions with varying levels of resources and RDM maturity. Finally, it will illustrate how the shared services approach fosters a more inclusive and cost-effective RDM ecosystem—not only within Austria but also in close cooperation with the EOSC Support Office Austria [6], which acts as a bridge to the broader European Open Science community.

Keywords: Shared Services, Operating Models, DAMAP, eLabFTW, InvenioRDM, Open Science

Resources

- DAMAP: <https://damap.org/>
- eLabFTW: <https://www.elabftw.net/>
- InvenioRDM: <https://inveniosoftware.org/products/rdm/>

Author contributions

- Alexander Bardel (Writing – original draft, Project administration)
- Ilire Hasani-Mavriqi (Writing – review & editing, Supervision)
- Birgit Söser (Writing – review & editing, Project administration)

Competing interests

“The authors declare that they have no competing interests.”

Funding

This project is funded by the Austrian Federal Ministry for Women, Science and Research (BMFWF) as part of the '(digital) research infrastructure' call.

Acknowledgement

The authors would like to thank the BMFWF for funding this project and all participating universities and their representatives for their support and intensive cooperation.

References

- [1] Open Science Policy Austria. “BMFWF” Federal Ministry for Women, Science and Research. <https://www.bmfwf.gv.at/wissenschaft/leitthemen/digitalisierung/open-science/open-science-policy-austria.html> (accessed 09.04.2025).

- [2] Cluster Forschungsdaten. "SharedRDM" Shared RDM Services & Infrastructure. <https://forschungsdaten.at/sharedrdm/> (accessed 09.04.2025).
- [3] Cluster Forschungsdaten. „Cluster Forschungsdaten“. <https://forschungsdaten.at/> (accessed 09.04.2025).
- [4] Cluster Forschungsdaten. „FDA“ FAIR Data Austria. <https://forschungsdaten.at/fda/> (accessed 09.04.2025).
- [5] Bardel et al., Business Models for RDM Tools and Services, Shared RDM Services and Infrastructure. https://forschungsdaten.at/wp-content/uploads/2024/06/Poster_Business-Models.pdf (accessed 09.04.2025).
- [6] EOSC Austria. "EOSC SOA" EOSC Support Office Austria. <https://eosc-austria.at/> (accessed 09.04.2025).